

LINGUISTIC-STYLISTIC FEATURES OF JACK LONDONS NOVEL “MARTIN EDEN”

*Iskandarov Bahrom,
O‘zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti doktoranti.
iskandarovbahrom111@gmail.com.*

Abstract. This article explores the linguistic-stylistic devices used in Jack London's novel *Martin Eden*, written in 1909. Recognized for its compelling depiction of early 20th-century American society, the novel's language is both rich and idiomatic, making it a valuable text for linguistic analysis. The study focuses on stylistic semasiology, examining how meaning transference and combination enhance expressiveness in the text. Through various figures of speech—metaphor, personification, metonymy, allegory, and juxtaposition—London creates vivid, emotive imagery that enhances readers' engagement.

Keywords: Martin Eden, Jack London, linguistic-stylistic devices, metaphor, personification, metonymy, allegory, comparison, epithet, stylistic semasiology.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются лингвостилистические приёмы, использованные в романе Джека Лондона «Мартин Иден», написанном в 1909 году. Роман, признанный за яркое изображение американского общества начала XX века, отличается богатым и идиоматичным языком, что делает его ценным материалом для лингвистического анализа. Исследование сосредоточено на стилистической семасиологии, изучая, как перенос и сочетание значений усиливают выразительность текста. С помощью различных тропов — метафоры, олицетворения, метонимии, аллегории и противопоставления — Лондон создаёт яркие, эмоционально насыщенные образы, способствующие вовлечению читателя.

Ключевые слова: «Мартин Иден», Джек Лондон, лингвостилистические приёмы, метафора, олицетворение, метонимия, аллегория, сравнение, эпитет, стилистическая семасиология.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola Jek Londonning 1909-yilda yozilgan “Martin Iden” romanida qo‘llanilgan lingvistik-stilistik vositalarni o‘rganadi. Erta 20-asr Amerika jamiyatining jozibali tasviri bilan tanilgan ushbu romanning tili boy va idiomatik bo‘lib, uni lingvistik tahlil uchun qimmatli matn sifatida ahamiyatli qiladi. Tadqiqot stilistik semasiologiya nuqtayi nazaridan mazmunning ko‘chirilishi va kombinatsiyalari orqali matnda ifodaviylik qanday oshishini o‘rganishga qaratilgan. London turli nutqiy figuralarni—metafora, jonlantirish, metonimiya, allegoriya va qarama-qarshilik orqali yorqin va hissiy tasvirlar yaratadi, bu esa o‘quvchilarning matnga qiziqishini oshiradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Martin Iden, Jek London, lingvistik-stilistik vositalar, metafora, jonlantirish, metonimiya, allegoriya, taqqoslash, epitet, stilistik semasiologiya

“Martin Eden” is one of the most famous works by the renowned American writer Jack London, providing insight into early 20th-century American society. London's language is rich, diverse, idiomatic, and presents fascinating material for linguistic analysis. This article examines the various stylistic language devices used by the author. Linguistic-stylistic devices contribute to the realization of the author's intent and play an essential role in the artistic work.

Jack London's novel *Martin Eden* was written in 1909 and remains consistently popular among readers worldwide. In creating this work, the writer employed various expressive language devices. This article is dedicated to exploring these devices and stylistic techniques. In this article, the stylistic devices are examined using the example of novel *Martin Eden*. We begin with stylistic semasiology, which focuses not on the unit's inherent meaning but on the stylistic functions of meaning transference and combination. The same referent may appear differently in various people's speech and situations, such as “young man”, “nerd”, “hat”, “donkey”, “pig”, “bear”, etc. In other words, names traditionally assigned to certain objects may be transferred to others due to specific patterns and associations: a person, for instance, may be referred to as a “donkey” or a “hat” In these cases, we deal with the transference (transposition) of meanings to create an expressive characteristic of the subject of speech. The mechanism and stylistic functions of meaning transference are one area of study within stylistic semasiology. Another area is the stylistic functions of meaning combination. For example, in the English idiom “merciful tyrant” or the well-known line “it was the spring of hope, it was the winter of despair,” an expressive effect is achieved through the combination of meanings. Accordingly, stylistic semasiology identifies two types of techniques: (1) stylistic techniques based on meaning transference (substitution figures) and (2) techniques based on meaning combination (juxtaposition figures).

Metaphor is the transference of a name based on similarity in features without actual connections between the traditional and metaphorical meanings.

Examples of metaphors used in the novel text include:

1. “with a wealth of golden hair” (p. 8) – “with a cloud of golden hair” (p. 9)

2. "...there was the servant, an unceasing menace, that appeared noiselessly at his shoulder, a dire Sphinx that propounded puzzles and conundrums demanding instantaneous solution" (p. 18)

3. "He was no gentle lamb..." (p. 20)

4. "...lily-pale spirit sitting beside him" (p. 23)

Through metaphor, London adds beauty, expressiveness, and emotionality to the narrative, creating vivid images. Personification is a form of metaphor in which non-living objects are attributed the qualities of living beings, thereby achieving a transfer based on similarity.

Examples of personification in the novel include:

1. "...his thoughts, sympathies, and emotions leapt and played like lambent flame" (p. 8)

2. "...and delicious little thrills crawled up and down his spine..." (p. 13)

3. "Her purity smote him like a blow" (p. 28)

Personification helps the writer create vivid images in the text. Metonymy is a stylistic device based on meaning transference by contiguity. This type of transference is based on real connections between the direct and transferred meanings. One variety of metonymy, in which a part is named instead of the whole, is synecdoche.

Examples of metonymy in the novel include:

1. "The eyes, weasel-like and cruel were looking at him complainingly" (p. 31)

2. "Behind those black eyes he knew every thought process. It was like clockwork" (p. 54)

Stylistic substitution using metonymy serves to create a more visually tangible representation of reality.

Allegory is a figurative expression of an abstract idea through a concrete image. The first allegory encountered in the novel is a painting. For instance:

1. "An oil painting caught and held him. (...) There was beauty, and it drew him irresistibly. He forgot his awkward walk and came closer to the painting, very close. The beauty faded out of the canvas. His face expressed his bemusement. He stared at

what seemed a careless daub of paint, then stepped away. Immediately all the beauty flashed back into the canvas. “A trick picture,’ was his thought...” (p. 7).

Martin Eden enters Ruth’s house and is amazed by its beauty, by the people he finds there who seem like superior beings to him. Then he notices a painting on the wall, a stunning, wonderful piece, unlike anything he’s ever seen. When he tries to look at it more closely, he’s disappointed – up close, he only sees brushstrokes, lots of them, and no painting at all. Here, Jack London hints that Martin will ultimately be disappointed in Ruth, seeing her flaws more clearly over time.

The use of juxtaposition figures by the author is also prevalent in Martin Eden. Examples of comparisons in the novel include:

1. “...he lurched away like a frightened horse” (p. 5)

2. “...the amused glance... burned into him like a dagger-thrust” (p. 6)

3. “Into his eyes leaped a wistfulness and a yearning as promptly as the yearning leaps into the eyes of a starving man at sight of food” (p. 7)

To achieve stylistic expressiveness, the writer extensively uses stylistic devices from semasiology, particularly substitution and juxtaposition figures. Metaphors, personification, metonymy, allegory, comparison, synonyms, and epithets are among the most frequently used figures in the novel. For added imagery, Jack London enriches the novel with a variety of idiomatic expressions.

REFERENCES.

1. Мандель Б.Р. Теория литературы. – М.: Директ-Медиа, 2014. – 386 с
2. J. London: Martin Eden. – М.; Издательство Т8, 2016. – 390 с.
3. Виноградов В.В. Некоторые вопросы советского литературоведения. Вопросы советской литературы. – Изд-во Академии наук СССР, 1956. – 265 с.
4. Виноградов В.В. О языке художественной литературы. – М.: Гослитиздат, 1959. – 656 с.